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Review Article

Telemedicine System In Health Care: A Review

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of review is to study telemedicine regarding to its necessity guidelines and the method of implementation .during pre and post pandemic time. Review also aims to study the digitalisation in health care system with its limitations and barriers for implementation , and the future development in the health care sector

INTRODUCTION

DEFINING TELEMEDICINE:

Telemedicine is a health-related service with the help of telecommunicating and electronic information technologies. It refers to the whole collection of goods designed to allow ill persons and their doctors or healthcare providers. It has a wide range of works, including online patient advice, remote control, telehealth wet nursing, and remote physical and psychiatry rehabilitation. It permits better health care choices, growing emergency service quality and performance, decreased time in making a diagnosis, and saves

costs for both doctors and patients by optimising clinical procedures and reducing travel expenses to hospitals (2,11). Telemedicine has increased permits to high-quality healthcare facilities. Patients will now get more customised clinical schemes. They can also meet the best medical providers simply by using video application software, advices can be taken from. Afar, and clinicians have better-suited tools for networking, information storage, report management and leveraging on each other's specific expertise. This better the quality of medical practice, allowing doctors to spend less time on allocation and

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providing more care to patients. Telemedicine also enables private healthcare experts to trainees and will enhance the patient involvement. Will no large have to stand in long queues, and physicians will be able to Access patient information more conveniently and efficiently with electronic files and eliminating overall wait times. Furthermore, remote appointments allow physicians to Devote less time to each patient, allowing them to treat a more significant number of patients (11,12).

Requirement of Telemedicine in the health care system:

Growing healthcare prices and a requirement for a better cure are to drive more hospitals to investigate the good of telemedicine. They want improved contact between doctors and distant patients and better usage of healthcare facilities. Here telemedicine also produced better connectivity, which has resulted in fewer hospital re-admissions and ill persons entirely adhering to their prescription care plans. Telemedicine's grown contact lead extends to physician-to-physician communication as well. Physicians may utilise telemedicine to build support networks to share their skills and promote better healthcare services. Telemedicine is a way of providing medical cure over the internet, usually through video chat. This technology has several leads for both patients and healthcare providers. Though there are still technical obstacles and critics, telemedicine can supplement and enhance the overall ill persons experience (8-10).

Background and Related Work

Telemedicine started as just the transmission of radiology images in 1940s between two towns which formed the basis for creating the Telemedicine platform (49). A Canadian scientist worked on the idea on 1950 and created the first sharing hub for the city of Montreal, this later developed into using video conferencing in hospitals for discussing patient's issues as well as remote surgery guidance from experts in the field

(49). One of the things that can enable Telemedicine is the incorporation of the Internet of things which allows remote health monitoring through peripherals you wear much like fitness bands, remote heart rate sensors, and devices that maintain, and send updates on any implanted artificial organs within the human body (50). Smart beds are now a common occurrence in hospitals which measure the patient vitals while they lay on them and could be used to send alarms in case of emergency as well as adjust the comfort level of the bed without any interaction from the staff. As of the date of this paper, an estimated 300 billion Dollars are spent yearly on medical innovation in the US (50). Tools that survey the physical factors are still being grooving using the open source and widely available hardware/software, what remains to be a trouble to this day is the expert of the end user who uses such schemes, they should be easy to use and quite user friendly as placing sensors by the end user might be a hassle. The work in advancement right now is trying to target the restriction in the available framework which is currently being utilised by products (49). There are many problems to be overcome before Telemedicine can be generally Used. Presently, in the United States, experts are required to acquire licenses in each state in which they intend to prescribe drugs and see patients . Moreover, legal priority for remote threat has not yet been built up. Repayment plans of action are additionally not all around well characterized. Teleradiology exams are the key Telemedicine sessions that consistently get repayment .. other real barriers to Telemedicine is the shortage of high information transfer capability in rural zones, which remains a noteworthy Problems even as Telecommunications organizations across the country are moved up to help the national information infrastructure (NII). Moreover, the underlying cost of hardware and the repeating costs of Telecommunications management are

significant. Not with standing, late acknowledgment and sending of photos archiving and communications systems (PACS) in healing centers and the Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) standard can give a substructure to encourage the Utilisation of Telemedicine frameworks . (5)

Acceptance of Telemedicine Implementation

The Various appeals have approved the implementation of telemedicine in a Comprehensive manner in various health services, which translates into multiple Profits for the general society .This has been reflected in the interest of the general Society in this form of health care. In the United States, through strongest matches of the volume of searches on Google, Scientists found that as COVID-19 cases increased, the number of searches and Interest in telemedicine increased, with a high correlation ($r=0.948$, $P<.001$).⁴⁵ Within The institutions that have executed telemedicine, this tool has been widely accepted By users and patients, as shown in various evaluations and satisfaction surveys. This Shows that the use of telemedicine translates to a high degree of satisfaction by users, Even more so when it facilitates advice for many ill patients who must travel long Distances to receive a medical evaluation by a specialist.³⁴ Regarding estimation, the Perception of health personnel should also be measured, for in the case of a low Appraisal rate efficiency could be low, as would execution of telemedicine over Time. In Ireland, 92% percent of the psychiatrists surveyed reported a decreased in in Detection confidence by not being capable of evaluating the ill person's nonverbal language. These key aspects must be taken into report to achieve success in the Execution of telemedicine because the doctors play a fundamental role. Conversion from telephone advice to video consultations would be better the Acceptance of this modality by psychiatrists. (1).

Execution of Telemedicine in In-Patient Care

The benefits of the execution of telemedicine can be transferred in the same way to in-hospital care, as appear in 12 Of the selected publications. In crisis services, the so-called “forward bracket” is a Concept that has been selectively designed for crisis scheme such as viral outbreak and catastrophes. It is defined as the procedure of determining ill persons condition before The patient arrives at the emergency division.⁸ Through a 24/7 assistance in which, via video calls- preferably between physicians and Patients-, signs and hygiene links are evaluated and, according to a Medical evaluation, further care is promoted. In New York, during the months of March and April in the NYU Lang one Health (NYULH) system, crisis forward triage was the first telemedicine service that showed exponential growth. Over the course of Fifteen days, there was a growth from 82 virtual consultations to 1336, of which 55% Involved signs suggestive of COVID-19; at 6weeks, they had more than 16000 Emergency consults related to COVID19.¹⁰ Through video calls, they determined which Patients were at high risk of deterioration and required emergency referral, and which Patients could continue remote home management, avoiding unnecessary visits, which Reduced the number of individuals in the emergency department and makes resource Allocation is more efficient. Other uses of telemedicine for in-patient care is as a Device for daily follow-up of hospitalized patients, allowing medical rounds via video calls. To ignore direct contact and hospital acquired contagion, ill patients are isolated with an electronic device. Additionally, the Utilisation of private protective equipment (PPE) was Minimized by ignoring direct contact. (1).

Execution of Telemedicine in Outpatient

Consultation One of the fields of greatest executed of telemedicine, even before The Covid-19, is outpatient consultation or virtual migrant control.

In the research for Continuity of Medical treatment, without exposing ill persons or physicians and ignoring Transportation to hospitals and unnecessary contacts in waiting rooms via advice, Virtual advice was adopted. This is clearly reflected in the migration That occurred from face-to-face outpatient Management to Virtual administration expand through video calls or phone Calls, otherwise known as teleconsultation. Our review identified 27 broadcasting that Evaluated the Utilisation of telemedicine in the outpatient setting. Various Hospitals in in the United States during the months of March And April experienced a massive migration to virtual care, Associated with a decrease of more than 80% of in-person Visits.10 In a record from New York City, the epicentre of the COVID -19during those months, the growth of tele advices was exorbitant, increasing from less than 50/day to More than 1000/day, representing more than 70% of the Ambulatory volume they were previously managed in 4 Hospitals.(1). Ambulatory practices of various specialties, in countries Such as Italy, the United States and India reported virtual Migration percentages between 60% and 95% of their usual Practice.13-15 Additionally, they reported a satisfactory control of different chronic pathologies, ensuing continuity of Care and a quick transition to virtual care through the use of electronic medical.(1).

Limitations and Strengths:

Our search was restricted to articles published until May 31, 2020, and due to the speedy advancement of data on this topic, new utilised data may arise for the implementation of telemedicine services in the short term. Furthermore, regardless of the careful search strategy, there may be another unidentified Studies. Our research was exhaustive and included gray literature, trying to cover a broad range of evidence globally. Among the strengths of our review is that assessable conclusions were

identified to support telemedicine execution .By focusing on the 43 Studies that reported quantitative data, we undertake objectivity in our analyses.(1)

Abilities and functions of telemedicine when used in healthcare management system

The concept of telemedicine and related services have now been well Established and proven for societal help. Fig. 1 reflects the various features and facilities Offered by the telemedicine strategy, specifically for the healthcare domain. It promotes Chronic health management, order compliance, remote facilities, care-for-all Under critical and severe patients s, etc., which ultimately allow this methodology to Assist the healthcare and medical care sphere. In addition, a series of tele wearables heals up the sick persons and keeps them updating About their health status in a different way (13,14). Telemedicine is an progressive Technology, and many call it disruptive innovation. Thus, to cater to a distant sick person, Telemedicine employs a scope of electronic transmission media, ranging from Teleconferencing to picture-sharing to remote sick person surveillance. Physicians may also utilise Automation to offer quality cure to their sick persons. They utilise to develop better IT assistance systems and learn a new way of file management. For example, a virtual Meeting encourages primary care doctors to receive consultation from specialists when They have concerns about the disease or treatment. Exam reports, history, medical findings, X-rays, or other pictures are sent to the expert for Examination to the physician. The experts can answer electronically, set up a virtual Appointment with the doctor. These virtual pieces of advice can reduce the need for Unnecessary in-person referrals to experts, reduce wait times for experts feedback, and reduce the need for unnecessary travel. Telemedicine plans are more utilised Where a physician can see the patient, diagnose a disease, and chart the experience .(2)

Telemedicine in healthcare: significant application areas

It has an approach to different treatment options, including primary care advice, Psychotherapy, physical therapy, etc. It promotes cure via the use of wireless technologies such as laptops and Smartphones. In most cases, video conferencing is utilised in telemedicine. Some schemes, On the other hand, choose to promote treatment through email or phone messages. Often patients utilise telemedicine in coincidence with their primary care doctors. This Technology is useful where a patient must maintain physical distance or is not able to visit a healthcare centre. It permits practices to sell extended or weekend hours without suffer the cost of having the office open. This also makes training more attractive to the increased number of patients who insist on telemedicine as a primary care provider Choice (26-28). It is a cost-reasonable and easy way to support people with severe illnesses in managing Their disease, being involved in their cure , and preventing difficulties from Worsening. Gives the useful applications of telemedicine for healthcare. Different innovative technologies are utilised in the field of engineering. Healthcare and their related field (29-32). These are helpful to solve various difficulties related to Design, manufacturing and to make sustainable environment (33-35). Telemedicine is Often utilised with link physicians operating with a patient in one place while experts are in Another to help them through telecommunication. This is highly useful to remote or hard-to-reach locations where experts are not readily accessible. It is utilised to perform remote visits at a low cost and time. The advent of the internet Age brought about useful changes in the training of telemedicine. The crisis of this smart technology is capable of HD-quality video streaming paved the way for remote Healthcare to be transport to patients in their family, offices, or related living centres as an alternative to in-person meetings for both primary

and Specialist care. Numerous people say that telemedicine has persisted in some way or another Since the telephone was innovated. One can send images instead of information over the mobile. Telemedicine is also an approved component of the way Healthcare is promoted in Various nations. It has a surprising number of uses, which permits patients to Plan a follow-up consultation by video, improves consistency with aftercare visit guidelines and reduces the pressure on both patients and doctors (36-38). Modern telehealth apps support telemedicine and bind an mutual clinical interface to software. Treatment of ill persons with minor diseases, exchanging information investigation information, or photograph findings are examples of noncritical events. Ill persons can also buy drugs and get prescriptions from a dedicated app. Close coordination with payment gateways. Here analyses and information transmission take place in real-time. These telemedicine systems are often merged; as a result, it permits patients and physicians to easily collaborate via a single app to chat and exchange data. It can be easily collected direct patient data and forwarding it to the appropriate doctor. This evidence may be a transcript of an appointment or a test report saved in an EHR system folder. In addition, it allows doctors to interpret data once it has been collected (39-41).

Telehealth in standard practice :

1. Remote clinics

Because of the interest in finding new ways to provide specialty medical services to people living in remote, usually rural society, governments have taken the lead in setting up telemedicine clinics globally.(42) The lack of specialty expertise was another drive toward out of the box thinking linking health care centres in the more developed nations. Setting us such teleclinics had clear benefits for the patients, as well as a substantial educational yield for the referring doctors. On

another front, health maintenance organizations can provide service to potentially new referrals in relatively under-serviced areas.(43,44).

2. Digital clinics

Email advices emerged as a way to provide rapid access, regarding nonurgent cases. This was shown to improve communication with the professionals, save patients time as well as hospital resource and increase overall satisfaction.(43)Video clinics have also been reported to be well received by the patients who tried them, particularly those who do not have easy personal access to their treating health care team.(45)Online triage Patient-led self-triage (which relies mainly on symptom checker and service directories) or health care professional led online triage (using emails or web consults) has the potential to reduce demand particularly in stretched services, although the evidence is so far not strong.(46,47). Therefore, more research is needed on how to engage ill persons with such interactive systems and its applicability in real-life training.

3. Online appointment booking

Outpatient hospitals appointment bookings and ordering repeat prescriptions digitally can improve patient outcome, pharmaceutical dangered and enhance the patients' knowledge. Online booking not only will help to save resources and minimize did not attend" pattern but will also result in administrative efficiencies. Meetings confirmation is sent now by text messages rather than the traditional letter. Patients check in automatically on arrival, and called to be directed to the consultation rooms, laboratory or radiology suites.(48).

4. The digital doctor

Will computers, simply, replace the doctor's counselling in the modern medical service?" "My physicians did not look at me at all during the consultation. He kept Talking to me while his eyes

were concentrating on the computer noticing my referral letter, Outcome of my blood tests and X-ray reports". These are samples of questions raised Recently regarding how technology can alter the direct physician-patient relationship and whether current technology has been functional or disastrous to the standard medical training (3).

Types of coincidental and non-synchronous programs used in telemedicine :-

Mobile merged health care programs

Society paramedicine Mobile integrated health care platforms support patients to be treated in their homes, with increasing level of health Assistance is provided digitally oversight by doctors to augment care promotes to person Who call via emergency numbers such as through 911 calls [2], decreasing the need to carry to the emergency department. This treatment promotes virtual emergency Consultations and allocate work among subspecialty medical practitioners [2].

Mobile Health ("M"health) application

Mobile Health involves the use of mobile devices and handheld devices equipped with internet access to manage medical care operations in managing medical data, analysing medical related data and improving overall patient experience. The mobile devices install the software application to approach their medical information and can be used by doctors to assist dissemination of data with other medical practitioners in real-time [1].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning decision making application

Algorithms are incorporated in telemedicine to Assist with conclusive disposition of assessed patients via remote analysis .Thus, AI Chatbot are arrangements to promote the latest data on pandemic including Suggestion on precaution and possible recommendations to the community. It also supports the real-time situation data to medical trainees currently, AI is being used to

develop COVID-19 screening tools that can be utilised to receive preliminary tests for patients who have signs and further suggest Treatment if necessary. Accordingly, Kaminski [8] disagrees that AI bots can be used to Hear high volumes of patient traffic caused by high calls to health hotlines during this Covid-19. Likewise, tools learning models have been utilised to predict the most likely Places of where COVID-19 might be high and can be deployed with AI used to Minimize and expedite the processes involved in diagnoses and tracking of the Infection. Importing COVID-19 sickness scanned information to machine learning can assist the algorithms learn and improve detection accuracy of the virus. (6)

Recommendation for Use of Telemedicine and Virtual Applications Telemedicine

Which is the use of Information and communications technology (ICT) to contribute and encourage long-distance medical-care. Telemedicine requires remote healthcare Services and also includes continuing health education, doctor practicing, and management meetings .It may also Involve the utilisation of existing programs and schemes (such as Patient portals) to encourage promote treatment to patients [9]. While telehealth utilisation in hospitals holds great guarantee, its quick adoption has created new risks that may impact Existing health infrastructure . Hence, there is a requirement to Provide

recommendations to medical trainee on the use of telemedicine and virtual applications. A few recommendations are among Other includes collecting data consent as it still applies to telemedicine , and it is key to point out related risks that can surface during utilisation of telemedicine to patients during each session when delivering medical-care Using remotely. (7)

Problems in the adoption of telemedicine training in making healthcare Services effective :

There are very typical and usual obstacles that are needed to be taken care of While looking to apply telehealth-associated practices for healthcare and its allied estate. The things must be very free from any kind of solitary loss, privacy revealing, Scams , inaccurate solutions, etc. As any of these problems may become a reason for Anyone's dejection, or the case may become complex as far as health sediments Are concerned (15-17).Telemedicine and other telehealth monitoring methods may Assist patients and physicians in managing severe health risks such as diabetes and Asthma. Suppliers will also follow patients at home after being sent out from the hospital or Recovering from an accident. Patients' mishandling is a significant source of anxiety For doctors. Although development in medication have made it easier to use Technology, device outages occur

From time to time. Healthcare management that are Considering adoption of telemedicine technologies meet with industry trained people. They have a Host of realistic options for trainees interested in federation of telemedicine into their hospitals, making the integration smoother(18,19). This telemedicine scheme helps physicians to interchange patient data with another doctor who is located in another nation. A primary care trainee will now interchange patients medical history and medical data with a doctor without being in the same office. Arrangements can relay data over large distances between systems, allowing one trainee To know what another has already done. As a result, there is less similarity in monitoring and fewer cases of inadequate drug management. A doctor can collect and share data with their patient using ill persons portals. Medical tools can transmit vital signs and other data to physicians, allowing them to make treatment changes. Patients can now send biometric data to their clinicians through wearables or remote monitoring devices such as parameters or blood pressure cuffs. It can access patient information from a dashboard or clinical decision support system, compile information, and show ill persons status in near-real-time (20-22). Telemedicine helps patients to share data over far distances and become a game-changer. Healthcare reports such as photographs, blood analysis, and other information may be shared in real time for proper patient evaluation. Overcrowding in emergency departments can be eliminated utilising telemedicine by making patients first consult with a remote doctor via video chat. Healthcare networks that have implemented telemedicine technologies will testify that it takes a beneficial amount of time and resources. Practice administrators, hospitals, doctors, and others must know how to use the device to achieve benefits. While telemedicine is initially prices, healthcare facilities can have a good return on investment over time due to more

ill persons and fewer employees. Using this technology, doctors can evaluate a patient's medical background, manage clinical examinations, and more (23-25).

Complications of telemedicine generalized clinic:

Telemedicine is also a type of medical Behavior; it is an online addition of the hospital's work schemes with the main body of Doctors and nurses. However, the ongoing form of telemedicine is extremely Based on internet technology. Although manual clinics use technology, the Knowledge system and affective communication among people in hospitals are Shaped by the skills of medical workers who learn and work in actual hospital Schemes. Therefore, Give their skills, high ranking medical staff should be asked when develop the online working plans. Without sufficient medical information collected works accurate diagnosis and treatment sense, and a careful error rectification and precaution system, it is impossible for doctors to successfully supply medical services online. Telemedicine has boosted the transition of incurable disease treatment from hospitalized treatment to interactive expensive remote/online treatment. Big data technology has been adopted to actively assemble and compare health hazard factors to identify health associated hazard factors and suggest targeted mediated plans Through an intelligent medical commitment-making technique. This technique, which can be utilized to enhance the global analysis potential of medical details and help physicians improve clinical commitment-making accuracy, has made the combined medical service mode of remote to keep supervise and intelligent detection for incurable diseases an unavoidable trend of community development.. There is an urgent need for medical institutions to share medical diagnosis and treatment technologies and patients' management information on scientific and technological service platforms to rapidly make

innovations in the medical service mode for chronic diseases. (4).

Upcoming development of telemedicine, an operative healthcare Model :

Humans are facing a lengthy fight with the COVID-19 plague, and we might encounter similar despite again in the future. This pandemic reminds us of the Necessity of set up a healthy work and lifestyle. With the growth of big data and AI innovation, differential health administration is gradually becoming vital health management; the trend of unchanged backdated analysis transitioning to dynamic, progressive analysis is also a feature of the big data era. Big information technology promotes people with new methods and approaches to know and transform the globally, which is an innovation in the medical industry. The current telemedicine system can nobly make it easy to diagnose and treat activities Of physician and sick persons, effectively assist clinical work, and realize customised Diagnosis and treatment. Telemedicine is not restricted by time and space, and it can process a huge quantity of medical information simultaneously, which can enlarge the selected users from patients requiring medical treatment to imperfectly healthy people and healthy people who only require health administration (Ren et al., 2019). Our current process of health administration is submissive, and patients accept medical intervention only when there is something wrong with their bodies. Medical interventions also target lesions to eliminate these facts to reduce pain or cure sickness. However, active health administration is a therapeutic mode that actively applies trackable excites the human body to enhance the acclimatization of the human body and thus Build up its function or reverse chronic diseases. The human body is a compound system with strong resolve and self-organization abilities. The task of medicine is to Fully exploit the traceable methods and means for completely using the human Body's

capabilities to excuse human diseases and improve the human body. Requires prolonged continuous dynamic trace to identify and evaluate the Personal health state and its evolution and to perform active interpose via the Overarching complete use of various medical methods to maintain the human body in a wellbeing. Telemedicine connects the needs of functional health scenarios because it can realize the cyclical intergroup management among clinics , work units, and families. Because the main scheme of telemedicine are relevant to work units and families, the motive of telemedicine is not only to cure diseases but also to perform anticipation and treatment activities with physicians being considered the health 'coaches' and the patients' friends and living styles, such as exercise and nutrition, the tools for treatment. (4)

CONCLUSION

Telemedicine is a health-related service with the help of telecommunicating and electronic information technologies. It refers to the whole collection of deliverables designed to enable patients and their physicians or healthcare providers. It has a wide range of uses, including online patient consultations, remote control, telehealth nursing, and remote physical and psychiatry rehabilitation. It allows better health care choices, increases emergency service quality and performance, reduces time in making a diagnosis, and saves costs for both doctors and patients by optimising clinical procedures and reducing travel expenses to hospitals (2,11). Improves the quality of medical practice, allowing doctors to spend less time on rural assignments and providing more care to patients. Telemedicine also enables private healthcare specialists to practise and will enhance the patient experience. Patients will no longer have to stand in long queues, and physicians will be able to access patient information more conveniently and efficiently with electronic files and eliminating overall wait times. Furthermore, remote appointments allow

doctors to devote less time to each patient, allowing them to treat a more significant number of patients (11,12). Rising care expenses cost of medical and a need for better cure are motivating more hospitals to Look into the benefits of telemedicine. They want upgraded contact between Physicians and far-off patients and better usage of medical management . Here Telemedicine also encourages better connectivity, which has resulted in hardly any hospital Readmittance and patients entirely adhering to their prescription care plans. Telemedicine's rise in contact advantage extends to doctor-to-doctor Communication as well. Telemedicine started as just the transference of radiology Images in the 1940s between two towns which formed the basis for generating the Telemedicine platform (49). A Canadian researcher worked on the idea on 1950 and created the first sharing centre for the city of Montreal, this later developed into using video conferencing in hospitals for sharing patient's problems as well as remote surgery guidance from experts in the field (49). One of the things that can enable Telemedicine is the incorporation of the Internet of things which allows remote health monitoring through peripherals you wear much like fitness bands, remote heart rate sensors, and devices that maintain, and send updates on any implanted artificial organs within the human body (50). Smart beds are now a common occurrence in hospitals which measure the patient vitals while they lay on them and could be used to send alarms in case of emergency as well as adjust the comfort level of the bed without any interaction from the staff. As of the date of this paper, an estimated 300 billion Dollars are spent yearly on medical innovation in the US (50)The work in progress right now is trying to target the Restriction in the available framework which is currently being used by products (49). Teleradiology exams are the main Telemedicine sessions that consistently get Reimbursement.real obstruction to Telemedicine

is the sparsity of high data transfer capacity In rural zones, which remains a significant Issue even as Telecommunications Organizations across the nation are moved up to help the national information Infrastructure (NII).). Moreover, the fundamental expenses of hardware and the repeating The value of Telecommunications management are significant. The various uses have allowed the execution of telemedicine in a comprehensive manner in Different health services, which translates into multiple benefits for the general Section. The various uses have allowed the implementation of telemedicine in a comprehensive manner in different health schemes, which translates into multiple benefits for the general community. It also reflects in the attentiveness of the general population in the form of health care . In the United States, through the volume of searches on Google, scienti found that as COVID-19 cases become greater, the number of searches and interest in telemedicine increased, with high connections with ($r=0.948$, $P<.001$..45 W in the institution where the Telemedicine is executed. Telemedicine is also a type of health psychology. It is an online prolongation of the hospital's work scenario with the main Body of doctors and nurses. However telemedicine gets extremely dependent on internet services. Emotion connections between People in hospitals are given shape by the experience of medical attendants to work and learn in hospitals , knowledge systems and the physical hospitals are now using such technologies. Hence on the experience of senior medical staff patients are consulted by these online working methods.(4).

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